

Influence of Nigerian Home Movies on the Behaviourial Disposition of Nigerian Youths

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the impact of Nigerian home moves on Nigerian youth behavior, emphasizing the need for government intervention to restore order and preserve cultural values through education, mobilization, and entertainment. Negative attitudes because of violent movies Therefore, it is recommended that the abundance of local films undergo careful examination prior to production and distribution in order to have a positive influence on Nigerian society as a whole. The proliferation of local films is problematic. we used 200 respondents as our sample size drawn from our research production amuwo-Odofin Local Government Areas (Lagos) to test the variety of interest. Also the survey research method of data collection was employed to generate information on the impact of Nigerian home movies on the youth. Three hypotheses in chapter four, two of The impact of Nigerian home movies on youth was investigated using the survey research method of data collection. In chapter four, there were three hypotheses; two of them passed the test, and one failed due to the violence connected to certain house moves. Tables, straightforward percentages, etc. were used to present the analysisThe study explores the impact of Nigerian home movies on the behavioral patterns of young people in secondary schools and tertiary institutions in Amumo Odofin and Lagos.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria, a third-world nation, has experienced the problems that come with our youth's lack of exposure to western cultures over the years due to mass communication exchange in the form of television shows and film production. Thankfully, in the industry, the home movies set to project Nigeria cultural values and at the same and satirized some societal, ill in our society. The producers also employed other bizarre makeup and dramatic ironies to emphasize to the audience the importance of national development.

Ideally, after five decades of Nigerian's existence, the Nigerian society can now boast of a thriving and exceptional film industry that can withstand fierce competition in the global market, despite the expansion of the British government's colonial film unit's operations in Nigeria during that time. However even before now, Because of the influence that foreign films had on them during the colonial era, Nigeria was heavily dependent on the importation of these films. As early as 1946, a few commercial theaters were screening films for an eager Nigerian audience (Onyero, 1980).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Crucially, the Nigerian government recognized the industry's benefits for the nation's development even before the significant turning points in the indigenous film industry, and by the end of the 1980s, it had placed a strong emphasis on the industry's indigenization. so that the new trend of home view has in no small measures, in contributed to the nation's development. Though the x-ray of the societal, social and development. Though the x-ray of the societal, social and moral ill s in our society. This has been adequately successful through the creation of local films, which are more focused on culture and presented to enhance societal perceptions than foreign productions, which have a tendency to undermine our cultural values and are imperlaistics, materialistic, immoral and violent in nature and there things are capable of being transferred to real life an Nigerian audience at large now devalued, dehumanized, degraded and destroyed the Nigerian culture during the canonization period and up to the mid 1980s.

In recent times, proliferation is being witnessed in the domestic film industry. Any movie store will reveal an abundance of different films depicting Nigerian culture. social and moral decadence in the society and its outcomes. They have greatly aided in addressing issues that are currently plaguing society. Notable movies that go in this direction, for instance, include. Living in servitude, the forbidden circle of doom, treachery, the amazing adventure, the evil passion, the Ekaba boys, etc. All of these movies have, in one way or another, exposed the majority of Nigerian society's social and moral decay, from materialism to advance fee fraud (419) and other crimes akin to the Osu belief system in Nigbo and material status, blackmail, scandal, etc. as a bane of Nigeria social problems with a view to finding solution to these social ill s.

Finally, this project topic streaming the impact of home videos on our children's behavior patterns, using Amuwo-Odofin Local Government (Lagos) as my reference point. Due to colonial imperialism and the dominance of foreign films in the nation, Nigerian society was previously dominated by

western culture. Due to this, the nation's customs and traditions—both of which were unquestionably sources of pride—were eliminated. Thus, the film industry followed the same fate, the society intoxicated by the so-called western film leading to the negative changes experienced in our society generally. Thankfully, the home improvement sector is evolving and taking on a new role in order to expose social injustices and their effects on the socio-political and to salvage, redeem and re-direct our social and moral existence towards a glorious day society. Also Nigerian youths have demonstrated a bad attitude brought on by watching violent indigenous films. This study on how home movies affect Nigerian youths' behavioral patterns was made necessary by all of these. either positively or negatively for national development.

Research Question

This study, in the impact of home videos from Nigeria on the habits of Nigerian youths, posed many questions out of which are:

1. How does economic situation in Nigeria influence home movies production?
2. Does the effect of Nigerian economy in home movies impact the conduct of young Nigerians who observe Nigeria made film?
3. To what extent do Nigerian filmmakers use the natural and human resources at their disposal to improve the social conditions of young people in Nigeria?
4. Are the home videos entertaining? as sources of relaxation of the Nigeria youths
5. To what extent has Nigerian film promoted the cultural values of the different youths of different ethnic groups on Nigeria to foster nationalism?

Research Hypothesis

A hypothesis is a statement of relationship between or among variables which is subject to scientific test or study, that will be accepted if it fails to achieve support by the responses of the study, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis.

Nigerian Home Videos Have a Positive Behavioral Pattern on Youth

There is a remarkable degree of conveyance among till the types of evidence that has been sought to relate to violent viewing and aggressive behavior of youths. Laboratory studies, correlation field study and naturalistic experience all show that for exposure to television, youths are often made more aggressive significantly as assessed by great variety of indices, measures and meanings of aggressive.

Hence it has evident that any meaningful improvement to be made though movies such as violence and erotic, emotional exhibitions should be minimized in order to enhance the prospect of achieving moral, responses and eradication of social ills. In the same observational framework, the factor that is frequently hypothesized is the youth's identification with the actor or actress being modeled in that film. Badura et al (1963) found out that young boys and

girls are more inclined to copy male actors than they are to copy female models. Also there are higher correlations of the use of aggressiveness with the view male and the youth's view of the female actress violence.

METHODOLOGY

In this section, we were able to receive and analyze in table and percentage as vivid as possible, relevant information obtained from the respondents through the questionnaire (demographic and psychographics). A total of 200 questionnaires were distributed to the respondent. They all were filled and returned accordingly. We shall be presenting data on the research topic below.

Demographic Data

Table 1. Determinations of the Number of Sex that Received the Question

S/No	Sex	Frequency	Percentage
A	Male	80	40%
B	Female	120	60%
Total	Female	200	100%

Table 2. Determination of Age Frequency

S/No	Sex	Frequency	Percentage
A	18-25%	85	42.5%
B	26-35	80	40%
C	36-45%	30	15%
D	46 and above	5	2.5%
Total		200	100%

From the above table, it was observed between 18 and 25 years old (42.5%), 26 to 35 years old (40%), 36 to 45%, and 46 and above (2.5%), according to the age groups among the 200 respondents.

Table 3. Distribution of Response by Marital Status

S/No	Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
A	Single	150	75%
B	Married	40	20%
C	Widowed	-	0%
D	Separated	10	5%
Total		200	100%

From 75 percent of people were single, based on the table above. indicated the interest of the study, the impact of Nigerian home movies on youths, 20% were married found in media practitioners and 5% separated also drawn from on students that make up the population.

Table 4. Determinations of Educational Level

S/No	Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
A	GCE/SSCE	80	40%
B	OND/HND/B.Sc	80	40%
C	MAS/PHD/and other	40	20%
Total		200	100%

Table 4's demographic data shows that, overall, 80% of respondents had GCE/SSCE and B.Sc./OND/HND education levels, respectively, while 20% had MAS/Ph.D. and other.

Table 5. Determination of Occupation

S/No	Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
A	Civil Servant	10	5%
B	Lecturer	40	20%
C	Students	120	60%
D	Media man	30	25%
Total		200	100%

60% of the population in the above table was made up of students; the remaining 20% were lecturers, 25% were media professionals, and 5% were civil servants. employees whose insights are valuable in the matter.

Psychographics Data: Effects

Table 6. Do you watch Home Movies?

S/No	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
A	Yes	100	50%
B	Not often	80	40%
C	No	20	10%
Total		200	100%

The table is determined by the number Nigerian youth who watch local films in the findings, 5% respondents indicate yes, about 40% not often, the rest of the respondent said no the above shows that most young people in Nigeria like watching home movies.

Table 7. Does Indigenous Films Portray: Our Cultural Values/Heritages?

S/No	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
A	Yes	20	10%
B	Not often	80	40%
C	No	100	50%
Total		200	100%

In response to the inquiry above, which sought to determine whether local films accurately represent our cultural values and traditions. According to

the data in the above table, 10% of respondents said "yes," 40% said "to some extent," and 50% said "no." it should be seen that the local film portrays title or no cultural value.

From the statement that up to 60% of respondents said yes, roughly 25% said to some extent, and 15% said no, we can infer that contemporary Nigerian film exposes corruption and evasiveerotive expositions.

Testing the Hypothesis of the Research

Table 8. Determination of the Hypothesis Which Says that Nigeria Home Movies Affect the Behavioral Pastern of Our Youths Positively

S/No	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
A	Positively	60	30%
B	Negatively	40	20%
C	Both	100	50%
Total		200	100%

This table is intended to determine how indigenous films' exposition affect young people's behavioral patterns; the hypothesis' results are accepted. Three percent of those surveyed claimed Nigeria. Film has a positive impact on young people's behavioral patterns; however, 20% of respondents claim that local films have a negative impact, and the majority, or 50%, are unsure, stating that home movies have both positive and negative effects. impact, the impact of these findings show that the hypotheses fall to hold general interest.

Table 9. Determination of the Hypotheses Which Says that Nigeria Home Movies Reflect Good Image of Nigeria Society this Causing Societal Change.

S/No	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
A	True	120	60%
B	False	80	40%
Total		200	100%

According to the information above, the hypothesis test is positive because it validates the premise that home movies have the ability to both positively represent our society and act as a tool for social change that advances the country especially in the youth's behavioral return through its messages. 120 respondentsrepresenting 60% of the support, 40% responded that it is untrue; thus, the hypothesis is accepted.

Table 11. Determination of the Hypothesis Which Says that Nigerian Films Offer good Entertainment to the Youths.

/No	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
	Yes	160	80%
	No	40	20%
total		200	100%

From the table II above, it became clear that the thing hypothesis also succeed with Out of 160 respondents, 80% agreed with the hypothesis, and 20% disagreed with it. As a result, the hypothesis supported malignancy and tested positively. Everything supports the idea that Nigerian home videos provide a good entertainment medium to youths, thereby reducing tension in the society for development.

RESULTS

Out of the three hypotheses that were tested, one failed and supported the alternative theory, while the other two passed or tested positively. This made it abundantly clear to say that indigenous films are genuine instruments for bringing about social change in the ways that young people behave. Finally, depending on the presentation and content, youths' perceptions of Nigerian home movies can be both positive and negative.

DISCUSSION

In this study, 20 respondents used to measure the variety of interest. The variables are films, the impact of home videos from Nigeria on the habits of Nigerian youths. Consequently, out investigation reveals that home movies influence people in both good and bad ways. behavioral pattern of Nigerian youths. Thus, some indigenous films contributed to violence in the youth's behavior such as ritual killing, cultism and Armed Robbery. Etc. while some movies with religious backgrounds and moral lessons play vital roles in encouraging positive behavior among the social life of youths.

Again, the three hypotheses tested in respect of this study, two tested positive all in support of good benefit of home movies to the behavioral patterns of our youth that is, hypothesis two and three (2 and 3) respectively were supported by majority opinion with frequency, 120 respondents in hypothesis two (2).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This work was aimed at finding out the impact of home videos from Nigeria on the habits of Nigerian youths using Amuwo-Odofin (Lagos State) as a sample population. Thus, our research, were able to discover that Nigerian

films have the potentials to communicate complex intentions, naming and desired and therefore have the power to change and influence the social lives of the youths in the society.

Moreso, In their questionnaires, many of our respondents offered suggestions for reducing the excess that filmmakers release to the public, particularly young people. They promoted government intervention in the sector to restore sanity and uphold moral standards and cultural values in society by educating the public, organizing citizens, and providing them with special films about the youths interest for national development.

In this study, the researchers made the following recommendations that parents ought to control and supervise their kids' exposure to violent corruptive indigenous films stock with religious lesson, decent in production and education for the moral growth of our children and wards towards proper behavioral attitude for better citizenry capable of contributing to nation building.

Finally, government should exercise stringent policy in theses indigenous film by way of regulations and at the same time provide good environment for quality production of home movies through incentive and promotion for quality production odindigenous films in the international market and encouragement of sound training for local producers, actors and actors and actresses for improvement.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has shortcomings because it still needs to be carried out further research on the topic "Influence of Nigerian HomeMovies on the Behaviourial Disposition of Nigerian Youths."

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